

“In my village everything is known”: sexting and revenge porn in young people from rural Spain

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Sexting, and the cyber violence that may result from it, such as revenge porn, have received great attention from many different scientific disciplines. The present study incorporates an important dimension in the research conducted on these expanding digital behaviours, namely place and its influence on the effects that may unfold. Our objective has been to study, from a feminist perspective, the practices of sexting and revenge porn, the gender implications and its consequences for young people in a rural Spanish context. For this, we undertook a qualitative methodology obtained from in-depth interviews (N = 40) carried out with young people (22 women and 18 men) between 18 and 24 years of age who reside in rural areas in northern Extremadura (Spain). The results show that transgressions of gender mandates through sexting pose a greater challenge for young women in life environments in which there is little space for it to go unnoticed. The characteristics of rurality accentuate the effects for the protagonists of the non-consensual circulation of images, such as greater social pressure or the devaluation of their femininity. The findings are discussed and contributions to the debate on the responsibility of young women in the agency of sexting and its consequences are included.

Keywords: sexting, revenge porn, young people, rural areas, gender

Introduction

In recent years the practice of sexting has received a great deal of attention from the scientific community, without their being a consensus as to its definition. This is because it is an evolving concept that is constantly adapting to the speed and changes that accompany the development and expansion of social networks (Bianca Klettke, David J. Hallford and David J. Mellor 2014). In this study, sexting is understood as the practice of sharing intimate texts, photographs and videos through the internet and social networks, for which the main device is the smartphone (Michelle Drouin, Jody Ross and Elizabeth Tobin 2015). Nudity and sexually explicit content may be included

in this content or not. They take the structure of selfies and involve one or several people (Soraya Calvo 2016; Jessica Ringrose, Rosalind Gill, Sonia M. Livingstone and Laura Harvey 2012). This type of sexting is framed within the categorization established by different researchers as *consensual sexting* (Nicola Döring 2014), *experimental sexting* (Janis Wolak and David Finkelhor 2011), or *primary sexting* (Carolina Villacampa 2017), which is carried out both inside and outside young people's romantic relationships, with higher prevalence in young adults (Jose R. Agustina and Esperanza L. Gómez-Durán 2016; Amanda Lenhart 2009; Jeff R. Temple, Jonathan A. Paul, Patricia van den Berg, Vi Donna Le, Amy McElhany and Brian W. Temple 2012).

It should be noted that the lack of agreement concerning a clear, operative definition of sexting has resulted in the studies thus far undertaken showing different prevalence rates, depending on variations in the research methodology or on the operationalization of behaviors (José R. Agustina and Esperanza L. Gómez-Durán 2012). Internationally, different studies indicate high prevalences of sexting (Temple et al. 2012; Donald S. Strassberg, Ryan K McKinnon, Michael A Sustaíta and Jordan Rullo 2013) including in rural environments, for example, of the US, with 54.8% among adolescent students (Anne J. Maheux, Reina Evans, Laura Widman, Jacqueline Nesi, Mitchell J. Prinstein and Sophia Choukas-Bradley 2020). In Spain, although one of the most recent studies puts the participation of Spanish adolescents in sexting behaviors at 13.5% (Manuel Gámez-Guadix, Patricia de Santisteban and Santiago Resett 2017), we have scant data on this phenomenon with regard to the environment under study (María Alfaro, Marta E. Vázquez, Ana Fierro, Beatriz Herrero, María F. Muñoz and Luis Rodríguez 2015).

Sexting emerges within the current context of the “sexualization of culture”

(Rikke Amundsen 2018) and takes on many varied forms, depending on diverse aims, such as: to satisfy the partner's desires and guarantee that the partner follow them (Robert S. Weisskirch, Michelle Drouin and Rakel Delevi 2017); to impress or attract the attention of the recipient, to be considered popular, or due to appreciation of the capacity for seduction (María I. Fajardo, Marta Gordillo and Ana B. Regalado 2013). Nevertheless, we should bear in mind the structural inequality and hierarchized gender relations into which these practices are inserted, where the sexual subjectivities of women are much more strictly guarded than those of young men, having narrow frameworks of purity and innocence, meaning that the women have to handle the punitive risks and pressures regarding their sexting behaviors (Molly Dragiewicz, Jean Burgess, Ariadna Matamoros-Fernandez, Michael Salter, Nicolas P. Suzor, Delanie Woodlock and Bridget Harris 2018).

The issue is that primary sexting can lead to criminal behavior, such as revenge porn. Following the definition of the European Institute for Gender Equality (2017), revenge porn, also known as “non-consensual pornography” or “image-based sexual abuse”, “involves the online distribution of sexually graphic photographs or videos without the consent of the individual in the images” (EIGE 2017, 2). This practice has been defined as: *nonconsensual sexting* (Amy A. Hasinoff 2012), *secondary sexting* (Ringrose et al. 2012; Villacampa 2017), or *aggravated sexting* (Wolak and Finkelhor 2011). It should be stressed that the assumptions that surround digital sexual self-expression for young people and adolescents continue to elide considerations of consent and the violence of these acts is minimized (Denise Buiten 2020). Unlike the practice of sexting, understood as the consensual exchange of material with sexual content, which is not considered illegal, except in the case of minors – who lack the capacity to consent to such acts – revenge porn constitutes a punishable behavior in the existing Spanish

Penal Code.¹ However, it is worth noting that there is even less data on this behavior, due both to its relative novelty and to it being rarely reported (Villacampa 2017).

In fact, it is important to stress the gender component inherent in these illicit acts. According to international organizations, this is a growing problem worldwide that disproportionately affects women and girls, and has serious repercussions in their lives (EIGE 2017). It is estimated that one in ten women has already suffered some form of cyber violence from the age of fifteen (FRA 2014), and women between the ages of 18 and 24 are at great risk of being subject to digital sexual harassment and abuse, as well as physical threats (UN Broadband Commission for Digital Development 2015). In the rural environment, moreover, there is higher sociocultural vigilance, according to the Internet Governance Forum (IGF) (2015), and this can lead to incidents of gender cyber violence having a more serious impact. In this regard, Jo Little and Michael Leyshon (2003) have already shown how rural communities are spaces where the dominant constructions of masculinity and femininity incorporate highly traditional assumptions regarding the body, and also reflect conventional attitudes toward sexuality and gender identity. Similarly, studies carried out in populations of young people who live in rural areas in Spain have highlighted how the double standard in sexual morality, and the constant control and criticism that women who do not behave in accordance with the gender normativity and male chauvinism that dominate social relationships are subjected to, are an ongoing incentive to abandon the rural environment (Cecilia Díaz Méndez 2005; Josep Pérez Soriano 2013). The study by Fátima Cruz Souza (2006) also draws attention to the higher and more effective social control in these contexts, where

¹ And introduced in Article 197.7 through Organic Law 1/2015, of March 30, updating Organic Law 10/1995, of November 23, of the Spanish Penal Code. Available at <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1995-25444>

there is greater difficulty in breaking from traditional gender roles.

We have been able to find very few studies that examine the behaviors of sexting and revenge porn in rural contexts in Spain, analyzing the role that the digital networks play in the effects that occur with young people, through an understanding of gender inequalities and power relations that are present in these increasingly common phenomena. Thus the main objective of this study was to examine through a feminist perspective the practices of sexting and revenge porn, the gender implications and their consequences for young people from a Spanish rural environment.

Materials and methods

In order to achieve this, we undertook qualitative research in which we carried out 40 in-depth interviews of young people between the ages of 18 and 24 years old who live in rural areas of the Comarca de la Vera, a county in the north-east of the province of Cáceres, in the autonomous community of Extremadura, Spain. We established a series of sociodemographic variables in the selected sample in order to ensure the heterogeneity of profiles and discourse of the reference group, for the purpose of discovering, analyzing and interpreting different perspectives: age (average age, 19.5); sex (55% women, 45% men); municipality of residence (22.5% <1000 inhabitants, 20% 1000-5000 inhabitants., 57.5% 5000-10000 inhabitants.); place of birth (85% in Extremadura, 7.5% other Spanish Autonomous Community; 7.5% other country); occupation (student 97.5%: vocational training, certificates of professional qualifications and employment workshops; in work: 32.5% in the primary or tertiary sector; or both study and work: 30%); in a relationship (52.5% with a partner); belonging to ethnic minority (15%).

The Comarca de la Vera is a Spanish rural area that has a series of unique

characteristics and specific imbalances that need to be taken into account and are key to orienting this study. The lack of generational renewal, the aging and growing proportion of males in the population, combined with depopulation, continue to be the longest shadows cast over rural areas in Spain in general, and in Extremadura in particular (Felipe Leco, Antonio Pérez and Ana B. Mateos 2017). Likewise, the Consejo de la Juventud de Extremadura [Youth Council of Extremadura] (2016) has highlighted the persistent abandonment of the young population from rural areas. The lack of training or job opportunities, low possibilities for emancipation and the absence of available leisure or job opportunities are given as the main reasons for deciding to emigrate to urban environments (CJEX 2016). According to data from INE (2019), the youth population of Extremadura makes up 15.86% of the total, with 169,404 people between the ages of 16 and 29. Extremadura has the highest unemployment rate among 16-24-year-olds in Spain, estimated at 46.31% (Spain 30.5%) (INE 2019), and a school dropout rate of 20.5% of young people between the ages of 18 to 24 who have not finished compulsory education and are also unemployed (the national average being 17.3%, while the average in the European Union is 10.6%) (INE 2019).

Fieldwork

Fieldwork began in November 2018. The in-depth interviews of the participants took place in three phases, from November 2018 to February 2019. The interview questions were designed around four thematic blocks that corresponded to the research aim: young identity; rural life; uses of information and communications technology (ICT) and social networks (SNS); and digital violence. Using non-probability snowball sampling, the participants were selected in educational centers, local organizations and youth associations from various municipalities in the Comarca de la Vera, Cáceres (Extremadura). The general criterion for inclusion was men and women between the

ages of 18 and 24 with normalized profiles living in towns and villages of Extremadura who were users of ICT and SNS.

Gaining access to the fieldwork was undertaken by one of the researchers who originated from the rural area under study. The contacts were made gradually and with the assistance of local professionals who work with young people in order to facilitate setting up bonds of trust, which enabled the location of safe spaces to hold the interviews in an atmosphere of sincerity. The interviews were conducted in person and lasted between one and two hours. We ceased carrying out interviews when we reached data saturation consistent with the research question, the theoretical position and the analytical framework adopted (Benjamin Saunders et al. 2017).

The interviews were transcribed literally. For the data analysis, we undertook summative content analysis. After the initial general reading of the transcriptions, we made a first identification of codes and categories, and then carried out a methodological triangulation to validate the categories (Sonia Gavira and Julio M. Osuna 2015). This enabled us to test the level of consistency and to resolve discrepancies. After the coding, the most meaningful units of analysis were extracted and the interrelations between the different themes were identified. All the analysis was developed with the support of Atlas-Ti software.

Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Ethics in Research Committee of the University of Granada (757/CEIH/2018). All adult participants in the study agreed voluntarily to be interviewed, receiving information about the study through a letter of commitment to confidentiality signed by the researchers. They also signed a consent form to be interviewed.

It needs to be stressed that, being a rural environment in which the people know each other and the participants and their behavior could be identified, the confidentiality of the interviewees was assured throughout the research process, concealing their personal data, using pseudonyms to preserve their anonymity and also anonymizing the names of the municipalities of residence.

Epistemological foundations

From the methodological point of view, this study was defined from a feminist perspective, giving voice to those who are most invisible – the young women who have not emigrated from the increasingly male and gerontic rural zones of Spain. This was understood as a necessary condition to make such meanings visible, contributing to their being taken into consideration to a greater degree when it comes to giving guidance for preventive interventions and social policies (Teresa Ortiz 2002). However, we have also considered that, in order to understand this phenomenon in all its dimensions, it is necessary to adopt a relational perspective of gender, taking it to be a social construction created and redefined through daily interaction with others (Candace West and Don H. Zimmerman 2009). We understand gender as a “performative” notion (Judith Butler 1990) in which femininities and masculinities are continually (re-)created within local “communities of practice” in the framework of gender power-knowledge relations (Carrie Paechter 2003). Regarding this, Raewyn Connell and Rebecca Pearse (2018) maintain that what it is to be a woman or a man is learned within a particular localized community. From this perspective, gender delimits, defines and expresses a social position that has the function of constructing individuals historically into “men” and “women” by a process of subjective appropriation of their norms and representations. This subjective appropriation can be grasped through the narratives that are produced and interpreted in qualitative research.

Results

1. Between value and risk: negotiations of sexual identity in the context of sexting

The principle of trust in choosing to sext runs through all the narratives from the participant sample, along with the undesired social consequences that can result from it, such as the possibility of the public exposure of images, which occurs because the relationship and trust break down over time and an inappropriate use is made of the images. The usual reaction is to hide it, because the boundaries of sex-gender normativity have been exceeded and something that is considered shameful has been exposed, even more so if it takes place in a small social context such as the rural environment, in which the mechanisms of sexual vigilance can be more effective. In this regard the following transcripts show how the transgression of these rules entails social punishments that affect the reputation of the people who participate in sexting:

I'd never do that, come on, because then it's like you lose your dignity. (Ernesto, 18 years old)

It can be used against you and maybe you get on really well with a person or you're really attracted to them and the next day you could get a serious slap in the face. (Gema, 24 years old)

Although the young interviewees did not personally admit to practicing sexting, from their accounts it emerges that it is a frequent behavior that is normalized among the young population. Only a few participants in this study state that they have done so, managing the risks and prioritizing sexual value, in that need (and attempt) to express oneself as legitimate desired/desiring subjects, in the words of Angela McRobbie (2009). Within formal heterosexual relationships, sexting becomes a habitual practice

and, according to the data, appears to be socioculturally accepted and justified (Antonio Gómez-García, 2019b), due to being within the boundaries set by morality in sexuality.

with my partner, who is now my official partner, I have done it (Andrea, 22 years old)

yes, that happens a lot, I, it's that I see it as normal, if you trust the person and you're together... (Mateo, 20 years old)

If what we observe in these statements is the “trust” that steers the practice of sexting, the unequal power relations and gender hierarchies, as well as the double sexual morality behind sexting, are made clear in the consequent devaluation of sexually active young women and in their embodiment of the figure of “the slut” (Antonio García-Gómez 2019a; 2019b). As Ravn, Coffey and Roberts (2019) state, the distinctions between what is correct and what is inappropriate are crucial for understanding the ways in which risk and value are related with gender in sexting, and how the description of “slut” is used as a stigmatizing female figure who does not adhere to the gender rules underlying sexting. In the participant sample, sexters are portrayed as “very sure of themselves” or “loose”, under the assumption that they do it as a way to attract sexual attention from young men. We can see this in the following interview excerpts:

I think that they are girls who are very sure of themselves and want some guy to notice them, and with the boy who they're talking to they send him the photo so he might say: damn she's hot! (Eva, 21 years old)

I've got a friend who came and was really kind of loose and she's even got a video screwing, and this girl in the town, I knew of lads who did say things to her.

INT: In what way?

- Like, what tits!, I don't know. (Nuria, 19 years old)

Along with moral assessments of the behavior, in these narratives we can see elements that demonstrate the objectification of the body of the women who see in sexting a way of valuing the dominant model of beauty and sexual attributes.

In the last excerpt above, one should also take note of the reference to “this girl in the town”. From a general perspective, the gathered information shows that sexting, regardless of the context, is a popular phenomenon among young people. However, one of the most relevant findings of this study concerns the identifying of elements or problems that are associated with the practice of sexting in the rural environment in particular. These include the easy identification or dissemination of personal and/or family data of the young women who practice it, and of those young women who end up suffering the non-consensual circulation of these types of images, as we show below.

2. One step too far: when violence comes into play and revenge porn appears.

2.1. “I haven't seen a single photo of boys”

Some of the most common phrases that emerged regarding revenge porn were, “they're always of girls”, “it's the boys who spread them”, giving an account of the power dynamics of the exposure of sexual images as explicitly gendered. This has its roots in the heterosexual matrix in relation to the categories of body, sex, gender

and desire (Judith Butler 1990), which attributes greater value to the images of women's bodies, the object of male sexual desire. The breaking of trust is naturalized as male behavior and young men are legitimized to feel themselves in a condition of power in order to obtain recognition and reward (Amy S. Dobson and Jessica Ringrose 2015). It is striking to observe how, despite the fact that the male interviewees do not admit to practicing sexting, in all cases they recognize that non-consensual circulation is carried out by other male peers. In the words of Alejandro, moreover, the predominant discourse of hegemonic and heteronormative masculinity on desire is made explicit:

I haven't seen a single photo of boys, nor do I want to [he laughs], but I've seen many photos of girls... maybe from having seen them through some friend: so look at the photo from Town 1, look at the photo of I don't know who... above all there from Town 1, from Town 2 no... from here from Town 3 there was one who they said... but in Town 1 I've seen one, which the parents had found out about and everything. (Alejandro, 18 years old)

It is noteworthy that, in line with what we have already stated concerning the rural environment, the young men and women identify the town of context where intimate images of young women have been circulated, which is not limited to their place of residence.²

2.2. *"They are passed around by groups of friends, they pass it to you, it gets spread around, you know?"*

² In order to ensure the confidentiality of the participants, as we have said, we have anonymized the names of the municipalities. Town 1 and Town 2 are separated by a distance of 15 km, Town 2 and Town 3 by 22 km, and Town 1 and Town 3 by 35 km.

The main ways by which the young men and women gain access to shared photographs and videos of others that have originated from sexting undertaken within a romantic relationship or flirtation between two people, are: showing the images from the smartphone itself, receiving them through chains of circulation, or uploading the photos to an SNS. Digital networks, therefore, boost this mass dissemination, which is not limited to the people of the town. The bodies of women are valued among the male peer groups as a legitimate practice and mechanism to gain recognition and worth in the group, which is in agreement with the study by García-Gómez (2019a), in which sexual activity with young women and hypersexualized achievement enables them to construct and maintain a high status of masculinity:

photos reached me of a girl from Town 1... and that with me being from Town 3...and now I do know the girl, but of course, I didn't know her or anything, I hadn't gone down to Town 1 in my life... so they split up and the guy takes it and passes it on... And it ends up... imagine it, if the one from Town 1 reached me, and then a friend from Madrid who was visiting showed me the photo, which he had on his phone... who knows where those photos end up.

INT: And what happens afterwards?

-No, you simply leave a comment and so on, if she's hot you say so in the comments, if she's not or whatever, but I don't know what ended up happening to the girl. (Abel, 18 years old)

I know a case of a boy from here from Town 3, who was with a girl from Town 5, and they were a couple and she sent him photos, and then when they split up he set up a Facebook account with her name and he uploaded the photos to screw with her... here in the town and ultimately who it ends up happening to, from here and from the surrounding towns, it always tends to become public knowledge. (Nuria, 19 years old)

That reference to “it always tends to become public knowledge” reveals the scope of acquaintanceship in cases of revenge porn, as well as the easy identification of the young women who are the victims of the non-consensual circulation of images and of their place of residence, contributing to their stigmatization in the face of such facts. In an environment such as the countryside, where there is strong social control, the young women who suffer these crimes are still more exposed and unprotected. To that effect, the case of “the girl from Town 1” whose photos had reached the hands of a young man from Madrid is particularly noteworthy. This shows how circulation is heightened through SNS, going beyond the borders of the town to reach not only people from nearby areas, as we indicated earlier, but also young men from different urban contexts.³

2.3. *“Now, as I’ve got this video doing things you shouldn’t do, I’m laughing at you”*

Another more common context in revenge porn is that of the break-up of a young romantic relationship, and the reasons given for it are revenge, after being cheated upon (or merely for suspecting it), or because the young woman has decided to end the relationship or has restarted her life, or when beforehand there have been arguments and anger and they break up. The norms and values associated with femininity in gender power relations therefore result in substantial risks linked to the use of the body of women as sexting currency (Ravn, Coffey and Roberts 2019), as well as producing a normalization of heteronormative masculinity as unworthy of trust (Dobson and Ringrose 2015):

³ There is a distance of 200 km between Town 1 and the city of Madrid.

she sent that to the boyfriend, within two days the boyfriend got angry with her and said: well, now that I've got this video of you doing things you shouldn't do, well now I'm going to send it out there with my friends and laugh my ass off at you. (Félix, 19 years old)

The intention is to laugh at her, or let's say you think the girl is doing something out there, or that the girl has left you, so you say: well I've got to do something, because this girl has left me and my ego is bigger than yours. (Laura, 18 years old)

2.4. *"They literally called her a whore"*

One of the direct consequences of revenge porn, when young women's position as an active agent in sexting comes to light, in line with what we have already stated, is the discourse of slut-shaming. Young women are shamed, in other words, when they occupy a place unsanctioned by traditional gender norms; and in this way the propagation of a respectable femininity is enhanced, along with the development of strategies of specific sexual control (García-Gómez 2019b). The value of performing more highly sexualized femininities in the current context involves a fine line that can easily be overstepped, with the consequence of being turned into a "slut" who is easy to pick up:

they literally called her a whore, yes, yes, a lot, above all insults. I think the teachers don't have a clue sometimes and the girl didn't say anything either, maybe because she was scared. (Juan, 19 years old)

yes, maybe they say well look at her, well she's easy, she's really easy, because since she's sent photos like that... well let's pick her up. (Adriana, 22 years old)

However, as we see in the account of the following participant, there is a sexually predatory masculinity in which the explicit images of the young women can lose value once they are “given away”, in line with the findings of the study by Emily Setty (2019):

if you show me what I can't see, what would I want to see it for? If I have already seen it without doing anything, if I haven't even had to bother trying, then that's that... I'll try another girl. (Abraham, 18 years old)

2.5. “If we see that girl, we talk among ourselves”

The rural context where this type of behavior is found is decisive for the consequences that occur. This is because, with the proximal nature of relationships in the area, the cases of revenge porn, according to what has been stated above, tend to be the talk of the town due to their rapid diffusion and the reach of personal and familiar contact between acquaintances. This has negative repercussions for sexters, who end up feeling the pressure of comments, judgements and looks of other peers due to practicing a behavior that is seen as “deviant” from conventional gender normative frameworks. Thus, in the towns, the use of the digital medium potentially worsens the normalized risks and threats to reputation of young women's sexual exposure (Dobson and Ringrose 2015). The discourses of social shame are particularly noticeable in the narratives of the interviewees:

the girl went and reported it, but as it's a town, if the girl reports, the whole world will know about it and the people will delete the photos and from there... they did almost

nothing... here in a town if a girl sends things it ends up getting found out and they end up practically kicking you down.

INT: And the whole town finds out?

-Yes, and very quickly, or at least the people I know did find out... if we see that girl we talk among ourselves. (Lucas, 18 years old)

The whole town found out... at first the girl was incredibly embarrassed ... people talked about it, they saw her then: didn't you see her, like? She was in class and she was hearing it and that was a small part... (María, 23 years old).

As we can see in the collected narratives, even if these behaviors are reported and the appropriate judicial measures can be taken, in the rural medium the victim can find themselves exposed to a process of continuous revictimization, as they know that they are recognized and labelled in those facts. This is in agreement with what has been observed by studies that analyze gender-based violence in the Spanish rural environment (FADEMUR 2020).

3. Dilemmas for sexters, between responsibility and freedom in the neoliberal postfeminist context

The young male participants did not at any time refer to causes nor did they talk in terms of responsibilities. According to the data, the young women, as protagonists, have considered the dilemma that sexting and its consequences entail for them. On the one hand, we have the accounts of those who reflect the dominant patriarchal discourse on the control of feminine sexuality, pervaded with moral connotations, through tough judgements of sexual shame and imperatives such as “respect for oneself” (Jessica

Ringrose, Laura Harvey, Rosalind Gill and Sonia Livingstone 2013). It is considered more of an obligation for young women than for young men, demonstrating the double standards of gender that, as Lara Karaian (2014) states, culturally and legally, have given rise to the sexual practices of young women being judged and punished more harshly, as well as their being held as morally responsible for their acts and sexual desires:

You don't know that person 100 %, not ever, value yourself and don't show things to others, because it's that, to top it all you harm yourself, because then the whole world is going to laugh at you, they're going to say, it's that you're such and such. (Lola, 21 years old)

On the other hand, the accounts of the young women who focus on the freedom of being able to express and negotiate their sexual identities, as well as the male responsibility in the violence committed, allude to trust and respect as fundamental principles that run through it. Thus, in the terms of the study by Amy S. Dobson (2014), the young women act with “performative shamelessness” or “laddish performativity,” fitting to certain postfeminist social expectations around being wild, free or “willing to do it,” as one of the few options available for maintaining a sense of self-definition and agency in the face of intense sociocultural scrutiny and gazes of sexual objectification (masculinized and heterosexualized) of the reigning neoliberal context:

If you are comfortable with a person, you can do what you want. If you feel like sending photos, you send a photo; if you don't feel like sending it, you don't send it, but if you trust that person to give them your intimacy, then let that person at least have a minimum of respect for you. (Marta, 22 years old)

Discussion

In this study we have aimed to reveal the voice of rural young men and women in the behaviors of sexting and revenge porn, shedding light on the intentions, consequences and implications of gender in the assemblage of these types of digital practices in a rural context in Spain. Thus this study adds an important dimension – place in the consequences of sexting and revenge porn – to the research carried out in Spain, since there are certain rural characteristics and determinants that can have enormous influence on the evaluation of effects for sexters, such as greater social pressure and devaluation on their femininity, due to the moral stigma that transgressing traditional gender commands means for them. In rural contexts, the mechanisms of social control are more effective, due to the close relations of friendship and family between the inhabitants, meaning that there is less space for this type of behavior to go unnoticed.

Regarding the consequences that arise out of this cyberviolence, preceding studies have already shown how revenge porn can serious damage the reputation of young women (Shelley Walker, Lena Sancí, and Meredith Temple-Smith 2013), create embarrassment (Daniel G. Renfrow and Elisabeth A. Rollo 2014), being judged with a double moral standard (Ringrose et al. 2012), and stigmatized as promiscuous (García-Gómez 2019a, 2019b; Rosemary Ricciardelli and Michael Adorjan 2018; Walker, Sancí, and Temple-Smith 2013). Similarly, the data presented here point to some of the existing barriers with regard to revenge porn, and are in agreement with those of the traditional forms of gender-based and sexual violence, such as: the fear of reporting, due to social repercussions that can be unleashed, thus leading to its being made invisible; or the feeling of impossibility of doing anything about it once the digital violence has

occurred. Along these lines, earlier studies have already given warning about the frequency of future regret over the practice of sexting, without any chance of doing anything about it (Fajardo, Gordillo, and Regala 2013; Walker, Sancí, and Temple-Smith 2013). Our results show how this is increased in rural areas, where it is very easy to identify the sexters and there is less anonymity for disruptive gender behaviors.

Although these patterns often coincide with previous studies, we wish to highlight how the characteristics of rurality accentuate the effects of the non-consensual circulation of images for the female sexters. The literature on these practices has been conducted above all on young people from urban areas, and it has not taken account how place can lead to greater scrutiny, if possible, on female sexual subjectivities. This is relevant in the current postfeminist context and the intersectional perspective that contemplates different social-structural variables, such as the place of residence, in the creation of severer situations of inequality and oppression.

In addition, this study contributes knowledge regarding the understanding of gender discourses in the construction and negotiation of young sexual identity, and it considers the dilemmas and positions that young women take in the current neoliberal and postfeminist context in a rural area that has particular characteristics. Similar to the findings of Antonio García-Gómez (2018), we have shown how sexual agency in sexting reflects contradictory discourses of regulation and resistance for young women, along with the tension that is produced between the reproduction of the patriarchal culture and the dominant neoliberal consumerism on the one hand and the presence of a discourse of female empowerment in line with postfeminist proclamations on the other. According to previous studies on the subject (Sue Jackson and Tiina Vares 2015;

Jessica Ringrose and Laura Harvey 2015; Setty 2019), what appears to be most difficult about the current context is to imagine the possibility that young women might have the legitimate right to mediate their sexuality digitally or to express sexual desire, as part of a sense of positive sexual self-definition.

Thus adolescents and young people have the task of negotiating a balance between desire and risk, just as adults persistently construct contradictory and panicked discourses around their sexuality (Jennifer F. Chmielewski, Deborah L. Tolman, and Hunter Kincaid 2017; Emma Bedor 2015; Catherine Page 2017). Along the same lines, an interesting study by Alexandra Fanghanel and Jason Lim (2017) has already set out the contemporary antagonism faced by young women, in which the “wanting to be free” and “to reclaim their space” runs up against the obligation to be safe and avoid risks, with its roots in patriarchal gender rules that define which behaviors are suitable or not. This means that, when the precepts of an appropriate femininity are not complied with in the normative gender framework by carrying out practices of risk such as sexting, the price is embarrassment or shame (Patrick O’Byrne and Dave Holmes 2007).

In this regard, various authors have previously detected that the variable of gender is essential to understanding these online phenomena, and that it is related to the current debates on the agency and responsibility of young women who engage in sexting versus the concealed agency of the perpetrators of gender-based cyber violence. We believe that agency should also be added to the people who contribute to the non-consensual circulation of images. Calvo (2016) has already argued that young women are more exposed, they send more photographs, but at the same time they are the center of the subsequent debate, in that the responsibility falls upon them for the problems

stemming from sexting. Hasinoff (2012) has likewise observed how young female sexters are often portrayed as irresponsible and out of control. In contrast, young men are not usually connected to the creation of these types of content, which is key to having a more effective response to abusive sexting: bringing to light the generally obscured distinction between consensual and non-consensual sexting. Meghan Velez (2019), meanwhile, has shown how the responses to revenge porn still place the responsibility on the women whose photographs are distributed online without their consent. This thus reinforces the double bind of victimization and agency, without taking into account the differentiation that exists between consenting to the creation of intimate content and its appearance online without permission.

With this present study we therefore open up a line of research that has been recommended by authors specializing in this issue, regarding the consequences of sexting (García-Gómez 2019a; 2019b; 2018) and on how young women from other environments understand and negotiate the value-risk nexus in sexting (Ravn, Coffey and Roberts 2019). The studies that analyze gender-based violence in the rural environment show that “in a town where everyone knows everything”, this type of violence is characterized by its invisibility and the particular vulnerability those who are victims of it experience, bearing in mind the fact that the victims either do not report or delay in reporting out of fear, among other reasons, of being judged by the people in their environment (FADEMUR 2020). In concordance with those results, many victims of revenge porn in the rural environment can find themselves in this situation of invisibility, intimidated and forced to carry out different acts against their will, faced with the threat of having their intimate photos or videos circulated. In this regard, what we have found in this study may only be the tip of the iceberg. It is therefore vital, in

line with the State Pact on gender-based violence⁴, to raise awareness of these issues in the rural environment, taking into account their particular circumstances. We also need to carry out studies of the situation of the women who undergo abuse, aggression and/or harassment in this area, as we have done here by investigating a criminal phenomenon that is becoming increasingly common. As the aforementioned Pact states in Measure 180, data such as those shown here are essential for analyzing the police actions, the criminal response, and the healthcare and legal assistance that need to be adopted against the various manifestations of this type of violence in the rural environment.

It would be worthwhile to perform comparative studies with young people from rural and urban environments, as well as in different rural areas of Spain that examine the specific characteristics of the place, in order to contrast and further the findings presented here. Another valuable line of enquiry would be on the coexistence of this cyber violence with other forms of gender-based violence, and to contribute to enhancing knowledge directed at preventive practice.

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⁴ Revised document of the State Pact measures concerning gender-based violence. Congress and Senate. Available at: https://violenciagenero.igualdad.gob.es/pactoEstado/docs/Documento_Refundido_PEVG_2.pdf

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